

THE EFFECT OF CONFLICT MANAGEMENT AND OPEN COMMUNICATION ON THE PERFORMANCE OF TEACHERS AND STUDENTS OF GRADE VI AT STATE ELEMENTARY SCHOOL 1 TANAH PASIR, NORTH ACEH DISTRICT

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the effect of conflict management and open communication on the performance of sixth-grade teachers and students at Tanah Pasir 1 Public Elementary School. This study uses a quantitative approach with a survey method. The population in this study were all sixth-grade teachers and students of Tanah Pasir 1 Public Elementary School, with a sampling technique using total sampling. The research instrument was a questionnaire that had been tested for validity and reliability. Data analysis used multiple linear regression. The results showed that conflict management had a positive and significant effect on teacher and student performance, open communication also had a positive and significant effect on teacher and student performance, and simultaneously conflict management and open communication had a significant effect on teacher and student performance of sixth-grade teachers at Tanah Pasir 1 Public Elementary School. The main problem underlying this study was the gap in teaching load between civil servant and honorary teachers and the vulnerability of bullying among students. The research method used was quantitative with multiple linear regression analysis using SPSS 2022. The results showed that partially, conflict management had a positive and significant effect on performance ($t_{hitung} 2.773 > t_{tabel} = 1.654$). Simultaneously, both variables have a significant effect with a calculated $F_{value} = 4.914 > F_{table} = 2.434$. The coefficient of determination shows the contribution of the independent variable is 8.8%, while the rest is influenced.

Keywords: Conflict Management, Open Communication, Teacher Performance, Student Performance

INTRODUCTION

Education is a crucial factor in improving the quality of human resources. The success of the educational process in schools is greatly influenced by the performance of teachers and students. Good teacher performance directly impacts student learning outcomes, particularly at the elementary school level. Conflict is unavoidable in the school environment, whether between teachers, between teachers and students, or between students. Poorly managed conflict can disrupt the learning process and reduce performance. Therefore, effective conflict management is essential for constructive resolution. In addition to conflict management, open communication also plays a crucial role in creating a conducive learning environment. Open communication between teachers, students, and the school can foster understanding, trust, and collaboration, which positively impact performance. Tanah Pasir 1 Elementary School in North Aceh Regency is one of the schools experiencing internal conflict, particularly regarding the distribution of the teaching load between civil servant and contract teachers and social interactions among students.

However, since the change in principalship, there has been an increase in discipline and performance among teachers and students. This phenomenon is interesting to study to determine the extent to which conflict management and open communication influence teacher and student performance. Based on this background, this study aims to analyze the influence of conflict management

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and open communication on the performance of sixth-grade teachers and students at Tanah Pasir 1 Elementary School, North Aceh Regency.

METHOD

This research is quantitative in nature, where the research method uses numbers and statistics to collect and analyze data. This study aims to measure phenomena objectively. The research location is at Tanah Pasir 1 Elementary School, North Aceh Regency, Jalan Matang Panyang, Blang Village, Tanah Pasir District, North Aceh Regency. The objects in this study are Conflict Management, Open Communication, and the Performance of Teachers and Grade VI Students. This research was conducted for 4 months from January to April 2025.

The method used in this study was total sampling, a sampling technique where all members of the population are used as samples. The sample in this study was 19 teachers and 26 sixth-grade students. Thus, the total sample in this study was 45 people. Data collection techniques used in this study were observation, questionnaires, and documentation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Validity Test

Validity measures the extent to which a research instrument accurately measures the variables under study. A variable is considered valid if its score significantly correlates with its total score. In this case, the technique used to test correlation is *Pearson Product Moment*, and decisions are made based on the test results. If the calculated r value is greater than the table r value, then H_0 is rejected and the variable is declared valid.

Table
Validity Test Results

Variables	Item	Correlation Value	r_{table}	Information
Conflict Management (MK)	MK.1	0.829	0.261	Valid
	MK.2	0.754		Valid
	MK.3	0.714		Valid
	MK.4	0.652		Valid
Open Communication (KT)	KT.1	0.487	0.261	Valid
	CT.2	0.571		Valid
	CT.3	0.464		Valid
	KT.4	0.506		Valid
Teacher and Student Performance (KGS)	KGS.1	0.478	0.261	Valid
	KGS.2	0.449		Valid
	KGS.3	0.454		Valid
	KGS.4	0.551		Valid
	KGS.5	0.581		Valid

Source: Primary Data, (processed) 2025

The results of the validity test in Table 4.4 above show that all valid questions where the correlation value is greater than the table correlation value, then all of these questions are used in the questionnaire.

Reliability Test

Reliability testing was conducted on valid items. The reliability test in this study used *the Cronbach's Alpha method*, and the instrument was declared reliable if *the Cronbach's Alpha value* reached at least 0.6 (Nurgiyantoro, 2000:312). The results of the reliability test are shown in the following table:

**Table
Reliability Test Results**

Variables	Number of Indicators	<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	Information
Conflict Management (MC)	4	0.779	Reliable
Open Communication (KT)	4	0.630	Reliable
Teacher and Student Performance (KGS)	5	0.663	Reliable

Source: Primary Data, (processed) 2025

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the reliability of the items in each variable has a value close to 0.6 so that the question items used are declared reliable.

Classical Assumption Test

When applying regression analysis, several classical assumptions must be met for the model to be used appropriately. These basic assumptions are essential to ensure that the resulting regression coefficient estimates are unbiased. If all these assumptions are met, the estimation results will be more accurate and reliable. Conversely, if these assumptions are violated, the coefficient estimates can be biased, potentially leading to errors in data interpretation and conclusion drawing.

Normality Test

The normality test aims to determine whether the dependent and independent variables in a regression model have a normal distribution. To determine whether the research data is normal, we can use the following histogram graph, normal *probability plot graph*, and *non-parametric Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS)* statistical test:

Histogram Graph

A histogram compares observed data with a distribution that approximates a normal distribution. Here's a histogram to determine whether data is normal.

Histogram Graph

Source: Research Results, 2025 (processed data)

By looking at the display in Figure 4.2, the histogram graph does not skew to the left or right and is symmetrical, this shows that the data is normally distributed.

Probability Plot Norm Graph

Testing data normality using a normal *probability plot* is more reliable than a histogram. This method compares the cumulative distribution of the normal distribution.

Normal P-P Plot of Regression Standardized Residual

Normality Probability Plot Graph

Source: Research Results, 2025 (processed data)

Based on the image above, it can be concluded that the regression model meets the normality assumption because the data is spread around the diagonal line and the data distribution is in the same direction following the diagonal line.

Non-Parametric Kolmogrov-Smirnov Test

In addition to graphical tests, data normality testing can also be done using the *Kolmogorov-Smirnov non-parametric test*. This test is a data normality test by first determining the test hypothesis:

H_o : Residual data is normally distributed

H_a : Residual data is not normally distributed

With the provision that if the probability > 0.05 then H_o is accepted and if the probability < 0.05 then H_o is rejected, as can be seen in the table below.

**Table
Normality Testing of Regression Models**

<i>One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test</i>		
		Unstandardized Residual
N		157
Normal Parameters ^a	Mean	0.0000000
	Standard Deviation	0.46652791
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	0.051
	Positive	0.032
	Negative	-0.051
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		0.640
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		0.808
a. Test distribution is Normal.		

the Kolmogorov-Smirnov value is 0.640 with *Asymp. Sig* at 0.808 and the value is above $\alpha = 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the data cannot reject the null hypothesis which means the residual data is normally distributed.

Multicollinearity Test

Multicollinearity test is used to determine whether there is a perfect linear relationship between independent variables, the regression model assumes there is no perfect linear relationship between independent variables. Detection of multicollinearity by looking at *the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) value* from the results of the regression analysis, if the VIF value is > 5 then there is a high degree of

multicollinearity Sumodiningrat, (1999:286). The results of the multicollinearity test can be presented in the table below:

Table
Multicollinearity Test Results

Variables	Collinearity Statistics		Information
	Tolerance	VIF	
MK	0.921	1,086	There is no multicollinearity
KT	0.980	1,020	There is no multicollinearity

Source: Primary Data (processed) 2025

The results of the multicollinearity test in the table above show that each independent variable has a VIF value <5 , this indicates that there is no perfect relationship between the independent variables, from these results it can be concluded that there are no symptoms of multicollinearity in the regression model.

Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test aims to test whether the model regression occurs when the variance of the residuals from one observation to another is different another (Ghozali, 2011). If the variance of the residual from one observation to another observation remains constant, it is called homoscedasticity and vice versa is called heteroscedasticity. Most data containing heteroscedasticity is *cross-section data*, because this data collects data representing various sizes. In this study, the method used to test heteroscedasticity is the *g lejser test*. The *g lejser test* method regresses the *absolute value of the residual* with the independent variable, Ghozali (2011). A good regression model is a regression model that does not experience heteroscedasticity.

- a. If the significance value > 0.05 then homoscedasticity occurs
- b. If the significance value is <0.05 , heteroscedasticity occurs.

Table
Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	0.189	0.228		0.830	0.408
	MK	-0.002	0.026	-0.006	-0.074	0.941
	KT	0.013	0.038	0.028	0.346	0.730
a. Dependent Variable: RES2						

Output results The output results show that none of the variables have a significance below 0.05. Therefore, it is stated that each variables do not experience heteroscedasticity problems.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Regression Analysis

Regression analysis is used to see the influence between the quality of regional apparatus, regulations, accountability on asset management in the East Aceh District Government, which is presented in the following table:

**Table
Recapitulation of Regression Analysis Results**

Independent Variable	B	T	Prob.
Conflict Management (MC)	0.121	2,773	0.006
Open Communication (KT)	0.055	2,884	0.008
Constant	3,776	10,020	0,000
Dependent Variable: Teacher and Student Performance (KGS)			
Coefficient of Determination (R^2) = 0.088			
Adjusted (R^2) = 0.70			
F = 4.914			
Prob. = 0.003			
F _{table} = 2.660			
T _{count} = 1.654			

Source: Processed SPSS data, 2025.

Based on the analysis results as presented in the table above, a multiple regression equation can be prepared as follows:

$$Y = 3.776 + 0.121 MK + 0.0055 KT$$

From the regression model, it can be explained as follows:

1. The constant of 3.776 states that if no improvements are made to Conflict Management (MK) and Open Communication (KT) which are considered constant, then the Performance of Teachers and Students at Tanah Pasir 1 Elementary School, North Aceh Regency is 3.776 on a Likert scale or Teacher and Student Performance is quite satisfactory.
2. The Conflict Management (MC) regression coefficient of 0.121 means that for every 100% change in the Open Communication (KT) variable, there will be a change in the increase in Teacher and Student Performance at Tanah Pasir 1 Elementary School, North Aceh Regency of 12.10 percent, assuming that other variables are considered constant.
3. The Open Communication (KT) regression coefficient of 0.055 means that for every 100% change in the Conflict Management (MK) variable, there will be a change in the increase in Teacher and

Student Performance at Tanah Pasir 1 Elementary School, North Aceh Regency of 5.5 percent, assuming that other variables are considered constant.

Based on the results of the analysis above, it is known that the two variables studied all have a positive and dominant contribution to improving Teacher and Student Performance at Tanah Pasir 1 State Elementary School, North Aceh Regency.

Hypothesis Testing

Partial Test (t-Test)

Partial hypothesis testing, namely determining the variables that have a dominant influence on employee performance, is carried out using the t-test, namely to test the significance of the regression coefficient partially, so that it can be compared which variables have a significant and dominant influence on asset management, which can be explained in the following table:

**Table
Partial Test Results**

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3,776	0.377		10,020	0.000
	MK	0.121	0.043	0.223	2,773	0.006
	KT	0.055	0.063	0.069	2,884	0.008

a. Dependent Variable: KGS

Based on the results of partial multiple regression analysis of the influence of conflict management on teacher and student performance using the SPSS program, the calculated t value is 2,773 while the value at the real level $\alpha = 0.05$ value, the obtained $t_{table} = 1,654$ means that the calculated t value $> t_{table}$ with a probability of 0.006 because the probability value of 0.006 < 0.05 can be concluded that the hypothesis is accepted. This shows that there is a positive and significant influence between conflict management on teacher and student performance, with increasing conflict management it will also be followed by an increase in teacher and student performance at Tanah Pasir 1 Elementary School, North Aceh Regency.

Furthermore, the influence of open communication on teacher and student performance using the SPSS program obtained $t_{count} 2,884$ while the value at the real level $\alpha = 0.05$ value, obtained $t_{table} = 1,654$ means $t_{count} > t_{table}$ with a probability of 0.008 because the probability value of 0.008 < 0.05 can be concluded that the hypothesis is accepted. This shows that there is a positive and significant influence between open communication on teacher and student performance, with increasing open communication

it will also be followed by an increase in teacher and student performance at Tanah Pasir 1 Elementary School, North Aceh Regency.

Simultaneous Test (F Test)

The statistical F test is used to prove the hypothesis that states there is an influence between the independent variables, namely conflict management and open communication, on the dependent variable, namely teacher and student performance. The results are as follows:

**Table
Simultaneous Test Results**

ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3,271	1	1,090	4,914	0.003 ^a
	Residual	33,953	153	0.222		
	Total	37,224	156			
a. Predictors: (Constant), MK, KTR,						
b. Dependent Variable: KGS						

Based on the results of the F test in the table above, it was obtained that $F_{count} = 4.914$ with a p value = $0.003 < 0.05$, while $F_{table} = 2.43$ so that $F_{count} > F_{table}$, it can be concluded that the hypothesis H_1 and H_2 are accepted, which means that there is a simultaneous influence between conflict management and open communication on the dependent variable, namely teacher and student performance, which is significant so that the proposed hypothesis is accepted.

Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

The coefficient of determination (R^2) is used to show how much of the independent variables of conflict management and open communication together explain the variation in the dependent variable of teacher and student performance. The results of the regression coefficient test based on Table 4.9 show that the coefficient of determination (R^2) is 0.088 or 8.80%. So it can be said that 8.80% of teacher and student performance is influenced by conflict management and open communication, while the remaining 91.2% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study.

CONCLUSION

The conclusion of this study is that conflict management and open communication have a positive effect on improving teacher and student performance. Conflict management also plays a role in

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student character development. Furthermore, a school environment that encourages two-way communication between teachers, students, and school management can create a conducive learning environment.

The performance of sixth-grade teachers and students can be seen in the synergy between conflict management and open communication, which creates a healthy, productive, and goal-oriented work and learning environment. The combination of the two has been shown to significantly improve teacher performance in teaching and student learning. This has a direct impact on task clarity, mutual trust, and rapid problem-solving.

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